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**ACTION RESEARCH
& THE CURRICULUM**

**TEACHER ELIGIBILITY TEST
ATTITUDE OF B Ed TEACHERS**

**HOMEWORK
HARASSMENT**

**CYBER CRIME AWARENESS
OF B Ed STUDENTS**

**CHANGING EDU SCENE
ROLE OF TEACHER**

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**TEACHING PRACTICE PROGRAM
ATTITUDE OF B Ed STUDENTS**

**JOB SATISFACTION
ACADEMIC LEADERSHIP**

**CREATIVITY AMONG
B Ed TEACHERS**

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A Comparative Study of Cyber Crime Awareness of B Ed (General) and B Ed (Specialization) Students

In this study which is undertaken to develop a positive attitude among pre-service teachers towards computer crime awareness, the investigators among other things find that there is no significant difference in cyber crime awareness among B Ed (Specialization) students and B Ed (General) students.

RESEARCH

The convergence of computer network and tele-communications facilitated by the digital technologies has given birth to a common space called 'cyberspace'. This cyberspace has become a platform for a galaxy of human activities which converge on the Internet. The cyberspace has, in fact, become the most happening place today. Today's students become the master in classroom by using more advanced cyber technology. Cyber resources keep learners active and encourage the effective teaching-learning process. But students indulge in criminal behaviour and practice abusing the cyber resources to transformation of information gathered through cyber technology. These conditions are termed as cyber crime. Cyber crime is a phrase used to broadly describe criminal activity in which computers or computer networks are a tool, a target, or a place of criminal activity and include everything from electronic cracking to denial of service attacks (Matthews, 2010). It is also used to include traditional crimes in which computers or networks are used to enable the illicit activity (Muthukumaran, 2008). Cyber crimes are technology-based crimes and the computer or Internet itself can be used as a weapon or means to do such crimes quite freely. They are organized and white collar crimes like cyber frauds, hacking, data theft, phishing, identity theft etc. Cyber crimes are committed with the help of technology and cyber criminals have deep understanding of technology (Thomas and Loader,

2000). In fact, cyber criminals are technocrats who understand the intricacies of information technology. Cyber crimes do not consider any boundaries or territorial barriers (Malik, 2011).

According to Pavan Duggal, Supreme Court Advocate and Cyber Law expert, "Any criminal activity that uses a computer either as an instrumentality, target or a means for perpetuating further crimes comes within the ambit of cyber crimes." The National Research Council, "Computers: A Risk", 1991 has stated: "The modern thief can steal more with a computer than with a gun. Tomorrow's terrorist may be able to do more damage with a keyboard than with a bomb".

In the Tenth United Nations Congress on "Prevention of Crime and Treatment of Offenders" which is devoted to issues of crimes related to computer networks, cyber crime was broken into two categories and defined as:

- a) **Cyber crime in a narrow sense (computer crime):** Any illegal behaviour directed by means of electronic operations that targets the security of computer systems and the data processed by them.
- b) **Cyber crime in a broader sense (computer-related crime):** Any illegal behaviour committed by means of, or in relation to, a computer system or network, including such crimes as illegal possession and offering or distributing information by means of a computer system or network.

Cyber Law

Cyber law was the first step taken by the government to stop cyber crime. According to Indian law cyber crime has to be voluntary and wilful, an act or omission that adversely affects a person or property. Cyber law encompasses laws relating to Cyber Crimes, Electronic and Digital Signatures, Intellectual Property, Data Protection and Privacy. The Indian parliament passed its first "Information Technology Act, 2000" on 17 October 2000 to deal with cyber crime in the field of e-commerce, e-governance, e-banking as well as penalties and punishments. The Information Technology (IT) Act, 2000, specifies the acts which have been made punishable. Almost all developed and developing countries have established rules and regulations to control the cyber crime. In India, the Information Technology Act 2000 was undoubtedly a welcome step at a time when there was no legislation in this specialized field.

Most of the cyber crimes are not new. Criminals simply devise different ways to undertake standard criminal activities such as fraud, theft, blackmail, forgery and embezzlement using the new medium, often involving the Internet.

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RESEARCH

A computer can be the target of crime, for example, when a person intends to steal information, or causing damage to, a computer or computer network (Svensson, 2011). The computer may be used as a tool in the following kinds of activity – financial crimes, sale of illegal articles, pornography, online gambling, intellectual property crime, e-mail spoofing forgery, cyber defamation, cyber stalking etc.

Need of the Study

The cyber crime has been a problem as early as the late 1970s. The first spam e-mail took place in 1978 and the first virus was installed on an Apple Computer in 1982. In 2006, about 2000 complaints relating to cyber crime were received and the major reasons for such complaints were financial fraud, viruses and hackers. It has also been found that there has been a constant increase in the number of children being exposed to unwanted pornography, Internet harassment and bullying.

Cyber crime is emerging as a serious threat in the world. Governments as well as police and intelligence departments have started to react. Indian police has initiated special cyber cells across the country and have started educating the people. Hence it is very important that students should have awareness about the cyber crime. So there is a need to study the cyber crime awareness of the pre-service teachers who are being groomed to be the future nation builders. Although there has been considerable study about cyber crime awareness, much of research has focused on adult conditions. This study is intended to review awareness of B Ed. students. The prospective teachers are the most important persons in our society. They impact students and other persons of our society very effectively. So it is necessary to make them aware of cyber crimes in their training period.

Objectives of the Study

- To find the awareness of B Ed. (General) boys / B Ed. (specialization) boys about cyber crime.

- To find the awareness of B Ed. (General) girls / B Ed. (Specialization) girls about cyber crime.
- To find the awareness among B Ed. (General) boys/B Ed. (General) girls about cyber crime.
- To find the awareness among B Ed. (Specialization) boys/B Ed. (Specialization) girls about cyber crime.
- To find the awareness among B Ed. (Specialization and General) boys/B Ed. (Specialization and General) girls about cyber crime.
- To find the awareness among B Ed. (General) students/B Ed. (Specialization) students about cyber crime.

Hypotheses

- H₁ There is no significant difference in cyber crime awareness of B Ed. (General) boys and B Ed. (Specialization) boys.
- H₂ There is no significant difference in cyber crime awareness of B Ed. (General) girls and B Ed. (Specialization) girls.
- H₃ There is no significant difference in cyber crime awareness of B Ed. (General) boys and B Ed. (General) girls.
- H₄ There is no significant difference in cyber crime awareness of B Ed. (Specialization) boys and B Ed. (Specialization) girls.
- H₅ There is no significant difference in cyber crime awareness of B Ed. (Specialization and General) boys and B Ed. (Specialization and General) girls.
- H₆ There is no significant difference in cyber crime awareness of all B Ed. (Specialization) students and all B Ed. (General) students.

Design of Study

The present non-experimental study is designed to evaluate the awareness on cyber crime among B Ed. (General) students and B.Ed. (Specialization) students wherein B . E d . Specialization students are exposed to ICT environment.

Sample

For the present study a total of 150 students of B Ed. were selected randomly from Bareilly city. It consisted of B Ed. students of age 22 to 30 years. Out of the total students 75 were from B Ed. (Specialization) from University Campus Bareilly and 75 were from B Ed. (General) from Bareilly College, Bareilly.

Tool Used

For the purpose of the present study, Cyber Crime Awareness Scale (CCAS) developed by Dr. S. Rajasekar was used to measure the awareness of cyber crime of B Ed. students. The reliability of the Cyber Crime Awareness Scale was established by the split-half method (odd-even numbered) using Pearson Project Moment Correlation. This only gives the reliability of the half scale and hence the co-efficient of the reliability of the full scale was determined by using the Spearman-Brown prophecy formula and was found to be 0.76 which is high and therefore the scale is reliable. The Cyber Crime Awareness Scale has constructed validity as items were selected having the 't' values equal to or greater than 11.75 (Edwards, 1975). Its intrinsic validity was found to be 0.87 and hence the scale is valid.

Analysis and Results

Mean score and S.D. of the raw scores were calculated and then 't' test was applied to test whether the difference between the Means is significant or not. The analysis and interpretation of the major findings and discussions of the result are as follows.

According to the raw scores Mean, S.D. and 't' value have been calculated which are presented in Table1. The Mean and S.D. of B Ed. (General) boys

Table-1: Comparison of Cyber Crime Awareness of B Ed. (General) Boys and B Ed. (Specialization) Boys

Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	't'
B Ed. (General) Boys	40	111.5	15.51	2.52*
B Ed. (specialization) Boys	45	121.65	18.09	

are 111.5 and 15.51 and that of B.Ed. (Specialization) boys are 121.65 and 18.09 and 't' calculated is 2.52 which is significant at 0.05 level of significance. Hence Hypothesis H₁ is rejected. So there is significant difference between B Ed. (General) boys and B Ed. (Specialization) boys. The result shows that B Ed. (Specialization) boys are more aware of cyber crime as compared to B.Ed. (General) boys.

Table-2: Comparison of Cyber Crime Awareness of B Ed. (General) Girls and B Ed. (Specialization) Girls

Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	t'
B Ed. (General) girls	35	103.85	13.25	3.77**
B Ed. (specialization) girls	30	119.07	18.41	

To test the second Hypothesis, the Mean score of B.Ed. (General) girls as per the Table 2 is 103.85 and S.D. is 13.25 while the Mean of B Ed. (Specialization) girls is 119.07 and S.D. is 18.41. The calculated value of 't' is 3.77 which is highly significant at 0.05 level as well as 0.01 level and hence Hypothesis H₂ is rejected. So there is significant difference between awareness of B Ed. (General) girls and B Ed. (Specialization) girls.

Table-3: Comparison of Cyber Crime Awareness of B Ed. (General) Boys and B Ed. (General) Girls

Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	t'
B Ed. (General) Boys	40	111.5	15.51	2.16*
B Ed. (General) girls	35	103.85	13.25	

From the raw scores Mean, S.D. and 't' value have been calculated which are presented in Table 3. The Mean and S.D. of B Ed. (General) boys are 111.5 and 15.51 and that of B Ed. (General) girls are 103.85 and 13.25; 't' calculated is 2.16* which is significant at 0.05 level of significance. Hence Hypothesis H₃ is rejected. So there is significant difference between B Ed. (General) boys and B Ed. (General) girls.

Table-4: Comparison of Cyber Crime Awareness of B Ed. (Specialization) Boys and B Ed. (Specialization) girls

Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	t'
B Ed. (specialization) Boys	45	121.65	18.09	0.59ns
B Ed. (specialization) Girls	30	119.07	18.41	

Note: ns = Not significant

* = Significant at 0.05 level of Significant

** = Significant at 0.01 level of Significant

As per Table 4, the Mean and S.D. of B Ed. (specialization) boys are 121.65 and 18.09 and that of B Ed. (specialization) girls are 119.07 and 18.41. The 't'

Table-5: Comparison of Cyber Crime Awareness of B Ed. (Specialization and General) Boys and B Ed. (Specialization and General) Girls

Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	t'
B Ed.(Specialization and General) Boys	75	117.3	17.66	2.34*
B Ed.(Specialization and General) Girls	75	110.37	17.29	

calculated is 0.59 which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence the Hypothesis H₄ is accepted that there is no significant difference between B Ed. (specialization) boys and B Ed. (specialization) girls.

According to the raw scores Mean, S.D. and 't' value have been calculated which are presented in Table 5. The Mean and S.D. of B Ed. (specialization and general) boys are 117.3 and 17.66 and that of B.Ed. (specialization and general) girls are 110.37 and 17.29 and 't' calculated is 2.34 which is significant at 0.05 level of significance. Hence Hypothesis H₅ is rejected. So there is significant difference between B Ed. (specialization and general) boys and B Ed. (specialization and general) girls.

Table-6: Comparison of Cyber Crime Awareness of all B Ed. (Specialization) Students and B Ed. (General) Students

Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	t'
B Ed. (Specialization)	75	120.54	18.09	4.80**
B Ed. (General)	75	107.12	14.66	

As seen from Table 6, the Mean and S.D. scores of B.Ed. (specialization) boys and girls are 120.54 and 18.09 while Mean and S.D. of B.Ed. (General) boys and girls is 107.12 and 14.66. The calculated value of 't' is 4.80 which is significant at 0.05 level as well as 0.01 level. Hence Hypothesis H₆ is rejected. So there is significant difference between B Ed. (specialization) students and B Ed. (general) students.

Educational Implications

Today when everywhere there is demand for change, it is computer as a nerve, which is so appropriate and most versatile device. Its use is prevalent in every field. So cyber crime awareness is required. The study was undertaken with a view to develop a positive attitude among pre-service teachers towards computer crime awareness. The prospective teachers should be aware about protecting their e-mail Id. and banking accounts and other Id. which they use on public place. Moreover, there must be awareness about issues like hacking, copyright theft, child pornography and pedophilia. The prospective teachers should be aware about the preventive measures of using computers and Internet.

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Sir/Madam

Please find enclosed the April 2016, Volume 15, No.8 issue of **EDUTRACKS**, which carries your article – A Comparative Study of Cyber Crime Awareness of B.Ed (General) and B.Ed (Specialization) Students.

As you know, we are trying to improve the editorial content of this magazine by inviting articles from the authorities in the relevant fields. Our ultimate aim is to make **EDUTRACKS**, the magazine of first choice in the field of education. For us to achieve our aim, however, we need support from eminent people like you, by way of contribution of articles.

While we thank you for extending your valuable support by way of articles, we request you to keep this support going. As for the topics that you may write on, you may decide on any topic that is related to education. All that we can ask for is that the article should be of interest to the readers.

We would also like to have your views on **EDUTRACKS**, especially your suggestions on how to make it better.

With regards

Yours sincerely

Circulation Manager

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